

A Review of Stackelberg Game Theory Model on Trade Credit

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Abstract:

Over the years, game theory has been used extensively to study interactions between the supplier and the retailer in business environment. Recently, a number of researchers have applied Stackelberg game theory on trade credit in centralized and decentralized channels. In this work, we reviewed the assumptions of the Stackelberg game theory model, its solution, its limitations and further extensions were also considered. Furthermore, how the Stackelberg game model applies to trade credit has been analyzed.

Keywords: *Stackelberg game theory, Trade credit, Supply channel.*

Introduction

Stackelberg game models have been used extensively to study issues in supply chain analysis (Zhou & Zhou, 2012; Cao, et al., 2022; He, et al., 2009; Ezimadu & Nwozo, 2017; Ezimadu, 2020). Recently, a number of researchers have applied Stackelberg game models to trade credit in which a supplier offers trade credit as a means of incentive for the retailer (Ezimadu & Ezimadu, 2022; Ezimadu & Ezimadu, 2023). This review focus on the application of Stackelberg game model on trade credit. We shall begin our review by first analyzing the assumptions of the model, its limitations and further extensions.

Most studies in the supply chain management have used the single period credit transfer where only the manufacturer who is the leader of the game provides trade credit to the retailer (Ho, 2011; Skouri, et al., 2013; Paul, et al., 2021).

However, there are many market situations where this is not appropriate, there have been some recent works that investigates trade credit transfer from the manufacturer to the retailer and thereafter, from the retailer to the end users using the Stackelberg game model (Jaggi, et al., 2007; Ezimadu & Ezimadu, 2023).

This work is organized as follows. In section 2, we introduce the basic concept of the Stackelberg game, in section 3, we review the assumptions of the Stackelberg game model, in section 4, we review the solution of the stackelberg game model, in section 5, we review the limitations and also possible extensions of the model.

Stackelberg Game Model

A strategic game is a Stackelberg game in which a player first pre considers his strategy and others

respond to his strategy in a sequential order. A Stackelberg game consists a leader and a follower. The leader has the power to pre consider a particular strategy, while the follower responds taking into consideration the leader's strategy.

The game allows the first dominant who is the leader of the game to set his price. He makes his decision due to the advantage it has over his followers. The followers then respond after considering their own cost and benefits.

Stackelberg Equilibrium

Definition: Let Γ^1 be the set of strategies for the leader and Γ^2 denotes the set of strategies for the follower. Also, let $R_2: \rightarrow 2^{\Gamma^2}$ be the ideal reaction function of the follower. The Stackelberg game exists given the strategy of the leader as ψ^{1*} and the strategy of the follower as φ^{2*} , the following conditions hold:

$$\max_{\varphi^2 \in R_2(\psi^{1*})} J^1(\psi^{1*}, \psi^2) = \min_{\varphi^1 \in \Gamma^1} \max_{\varphi^2 \in R_2(\varphi^1)} J^1(\varphi^1, \varphi^2) \quad (1)$$

And

$$\varphi^{2*} \in R_2(\psi^{1*}) \quad (2)$$

We therefore consider the following theorem

Theorem 1

In a non-infinite game with two players, there always exist a Stackelberg equilibrium in pure strategies.

Proof

We assume a game where player 1 is the leader and player 2 is the follower. Γ^1 and Γ^2 are infinite for a finite game. And thus, the ideal optimal response function of the follower R_2 for any of its strategy φ^1 maps to a non-empty set that is finite. But if the leader equilibrium strategy φ^{1*} , then there also exists a strategy for the follower say,

$$\varphi^{2*} \in R_2(\psi^{1*}) \quad (3)$$

When determining the equilibrium strategy for the leader, we often find a minimum or a maximum for the finite non-empty sets. Since there exist an extremum over the non-empty set, there also exist a Stackelberg equilibrium strategy (φ^1, φ^2) in a finite two player game.

The Assumptions of the Stackelberg Game Model

We assume a linear demand

$$F(Z) = a - bZ \quad (4)$$

Where b is the slope of the demand curve and a is the intercept.

In a sequential game or Stackelberg game, we first solve the problem in the second scenario, and afterwards the problem in the first scenario is solved. This process is known as backward induction.

The second scenario

For the second scenario, player 2 chooses p_2 given that player 1 has chosen in the first scenario p_1 where c is the cost incurred,

$$\max_{p_2} \Pi^2 = (F(p_1 + p_2) - c)p_2 = (a - b(p_1 + p_2) - c)p_2 \quad (5)$$

The first order condition (FOC) is given as

$$\frac{\partial \Pi^2}{\partial p_2} = 0,$$

this implies that

$$a - 2bp_2 - bp_1 - c = 0$$

$$\Leftrightarrow p_2^* = R_2(p_1) = \frac{a - bp_1 - c}{2b} \quad (6)$$

The first scenario

In the first scenario, player 1 chooses p_1 knowing fully that player 2 will react to it in the second scenario based on his reaction function $p_2 = R_2(p_1)$

$$\max_{p_1} \Pi^1 = (F(p_1 + p_2) - c)p_1 = (a - b(p_1 + R_2(p_1)) - c)p_1 \quad (7)$$

The First Order Condition (FOC) is given as

$$\frac{\partial \Pi^1}{\partial p_1} = 0, \quad (8)$$

this implies that

$$a - 2bp_1 - bR_2(p_1) - bp_1 R_2''(q_1) - c = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow a - 2bp_1 - b \left[\frac{a - bp_1 - c}{2b} \right] + bp_1 \frac{1}{2} - c = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a-c}{2} \right) - 2bp_1 + bp_1 \frac{1}{2} + bp_1 \frac{1}{2} = 0$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a-c}{2} \right) - bp_1 = 0$$

$$\Leftrightarrow p_1^* = \frac{a-c}{2b} = \frac{3}{2} p_1^N > p_1^N = \frac{a-c}{3b} \quad (11)$$

Given p_1^* , we solve for p_2

$$\begin{aligned} p_2^* &= \frac{a-c}{2b} - \frac{1}{2} p_1^* = \frac{a-c}{2b} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{a-c}{2b} \right) \\ &= \left(\frac{a-c}{4b} \right) = \frac{3}{4} p_2^N < p_2^N \end{aligned}$$

This means that $p_1^* > p_2^*$

Thus,

$$p_1^* + p_2^* = \frac{a-c}{2b} + \frac{a-c}{4b} = \frac{3(a-c)}{4b} > \frac{2(a-c)}{3b} = Z^N \quad (13)$$

$$F^* = a - bZ^* = a - b \frac{3(a-c)}{4b} = \frac{a+3c}{4} > c \quad (14)$$

That is, $a > c$

But

$$F^* < \frac{a+2c}{3} = F^N$$

Therefore, the equilibrium profit of both players is

$$\Pi^{1*} = (F^* - c)p_1^* = \left\{ \frac{a+3c}{4} - c \right\} \left\{ \frac{a-c}{2b} \right\} \quad (15)$$

$$= \left\{ \frac{a-c}{4} \right\} \left\{ \frac{a-c}{2b} \right\}$$

$$= \frac{(a-c)^2}{8b} > \Pi_1^N = \frac{(a-c)^2}{9b} \quad (16)$$

Therefore,

$$\Pi^{2*} = (F^* - c)p_2^* = \left\{ \frac{a+3c}{4} - c \right\} \left\{ \frac{a-c}{4b} \right\} = \left\{ \frac{a-c}{4} \right\} \left\{ \frac{a-c}{4b} \right\} \quad (17)$$

$$= \frac{(a-c)^2}{16b} < \Pi_2^N = \frac{(a-c)^2}{9b} \quad (18)$$

The profit of player 1 must to an extent be large as that of the Cournot. This is due to the fact

that player 1 could have obtained the Cournot profits by choosing the Cournot quantity p_1^N , to

which firm 2 would respond with its Cournot quantity $p_2^N = R_2(q_1^N)$.

Table 1. Assumptions of the Stackelberg game theory model

	Researchers	Assumptions based on the Stackelberg game model	Decision Variables	Channel Description
1	Wu et al (2021)	A risk-averse retailer and a supplier	Optimal order quantity, loss sharing ratio	Centralized Channel
2	Wang et al (2016)	One manufacturer, one retailer	Supplier's capital constraint, optimal decisions	Centralized Channel
3	Zhou and Zhou (2013)	One manufacturer, one retailer	Unconditional trade credit, conditional trade credit	Centralized channel
4	Zhang et al (2021)	One manufacturer one retailer	Trade credit period and optimal replenishment cycle time	Centralized and decentralized chain
5	Ezimadu and Ezimadu (2022)	One manufacturer, two retailers	Optimal promotion effort, credit period and players payoffs	Decentralized supply channel
6	Emtehani et al (2023)	Multi-leader and a financially constrained manufacturer	Capital shortages and financing restrictions	Decentralized
7	Ezimadu and Ezimadu (2023)	one manufacturer, one distributor, one retailer	Promotion effort, price margins and credit period	Centralized supply channel
8	Shen and Liang (2009)	One supplier, one retailer	Optimal delay-in-payments optimal ordering policy	Centralized supply channel
9	Wu and Zhao (2017)	A supplier and a retailer	Time-varying demand, time-varying price and learning-curve production cost	Centralized
10	Wu et al (2017)	One Supplier and one retailer	Quantity demanded and default risk	Centralized
11	Ezimadu and Ezimadu (2023)	One Supplier and one retailer	Product promotion, trade credit and credit period	Centralized
12	Qin et al (2021)	A capital-constraint bricks-and-mortar retailer and a manufacturer	Supplementary pricing strategy and competitive pricing strategy	Centralized and decentralized

The Solution of the Stackelberg Game Model

A Stackelberg game assumes fulfillment of the following axioms in which the players choose their strategies in a sequential form:

- (a) the first player selects his strategy $s_1 \in S_1$ and informs the second player about his choice,
- (b) the second player selects his strategy $s_2 \in S_2$ and informs the third player about the choices s_1, s_2 , and so on,

At last the n th player selects his strategy $s_n \in S_n$ being informed about the choices s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{n-1} , of the preceding players;

Backward induction is a method employed in solving stackelberg games. This is done by starting from the end of the game and working backwards. The idea is to find the optimal action for each player at each node, the players are rational and will choose the action that maximizes their payoffs.

We solve a sequential game by backward induction, as follows: When player two gets the move at the second stage of the game, he will

face the following problem, given the action a_1 previously chosen by player 1:

$$\max_{a_2 \in A_2} u_2(a_1, a_2) \quad (19)$$

We assume for each a_1 in A_1 , player 2's optimization problem has a unique solution, denoted by $R_2(a_1)$. This is player 2's best response (or reaction) to player 1's action. Since player 1 can solve 2's problem as well as 2 can, player 1 should anticipate player 2's reaction to each action a_1 that 1 might take, so player 1's problem at the first instance is

$$\max_{a_1 \in A_1} u_1(a_1, R_2(a_1)) \quad (20)$$

Assume that this optimization problem for player 1 also has a unique solution, denoted by a_1^* . We will call $(a_1, R_2(a_1^*))$ the backwards-induction outcome of the game.

The Limitations of the Stackelberg Game Model

The assumptions made for the Stackelberg game model result in many limitations for practical applications. First, the leader must know beforehand that the follower observes its action and the follower must have no means of committing to a future non-Stackelberg leader action. Second, moving first may be possible if the leader was the incumbent monopoly of the business and the follower is a new entrant, so the leader must have commitment power. Third, if after the leader had selected his equilibrium quantity and the follower deviated from the equilibrium and chose some optimal quantity, it would not only hurt itself, but it could also hurt the leader. Fifth, in a compliment relationship or when there are substitutes, the second mover earns the lowest profit, the third mover earns the highest expected profit of the three at a perfectly known equilibrium. Shinkai (2000).

6 Possible extensions of the Stackelberg game model

The work can be extended by considering a model involving multiple manufacturers and retailers. Also, there is the surety of a competition in which the players decide on their action independently leading to a Nash game. Another extension is to consider a channel setting where the retailer is more powerful than the manufacturer making the retailer is the channel leader. (Huang et al 2002).

The Stackelberg game model can be extended to consider a channel setting where the manufacturer can bypass the distributor to finance the retailer for a three-player channel.

We can also consider a situation where none of the players is the channel leader, this situation can arise when all channel members consider themselves very powerful and independent and in such situation a Nash game will be used.

References

- Cao, B.-B., You, T.-H., Ou, C., Zhu, H., & Liu, C.-Y. (2022). Optimizing payment schemes in a decentralized supply chain: A Stackelberg game with quality investment and bank credit. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 168, Article 108077. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2022.108077>
- Ezimidu, P.E. & Ezimidu, S.O. (2022). Modelling a manufacturer-retailers trade credit supply chain using game theory. *World Journal of Science and Technology*, 14(1), 80-85. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/wojast.v14i1b.80>
- Emtehani, F., Nahavandi, N., & Rafiei, F.M. (2023). Trade credit financing for supply chain coordination under financial challenges: a multi-leader–follower game approach. *Financial Innovation*, 9, 1-39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-022-00401-1>
- Ezimidu, P. E., & Ezimidu, S. O. (2022). A Game-Theoretic Credit Period and Promotion Model in a Supplier-Retailer Channel. *Asian Research Journal of Mathematics*, 18(11), 351–361.

<https://doi.org/10.9734/arjom/2022/v18i11609>

Ezimadu, S.O. & Ezimadu, P.E. (2023a). A three-level game-theoretic trade credit model in a supply channel. *Journal of Advances in Mathematics and Computer Science*, 38(7), 146-159.

Ezimadu, S. O., & Ezimadu, P. E. (2023b). A Mathematical Model of Optimal Manufacturer-Retailer Trade Credit Policy with End-User Credit Support. *Asian Research Journal of Mathematics*, 19(5), 61–71. <https://doi.org/10.9734/arjom/2023/v19i5660>

Ezimadu, S.O. & Ezimadu, P.E. (2023c), A stackelberg game-theoretic retailer-manufacturer credit period ratio model in a supply channel. *Science World Journal*, 18(1), 48-54.

Ezimadu, P.E., & Nwozo, C.R. (2017). Stochastic cooperative advertising in a manufacturer–retailer decentralized supply channel. *Journal of Industrial Engineering, International*, 13(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S40092-016-0164-8>

Ezimadu, P.E. (2020). Modelling cooperative advertising decisions in a manufacturer-distributor-retailer supply chain using game theory. *Yugoslav Journal of Operations Research*, 30(2) 147-176. <https://doi.org/10.2298/yjor181115001e>

Huang, Z., Li, S. X. & Mahajan, V. (2002). An Analysis of Manufacturer-Retailer Supply Chain Coordination in Cooperative Advertising. *Decision Sciences*, 33(3), 469-494. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5915.2002.tb01652.x>

He, X., Prasad, A. & Sethi, S.P. (2007). Cooperative advertising and pricing in a dynamic stochastic supply chain: feedback stackelberg strategies. *Production and Operations Management*, 18(1), 78-94. <http://doi.org/10.1109/PICMET.2008.4599783>

Ho, C.-H. (2011). The optimal integrated inventory policy with price-and-credit-linked demand under two-level trade credit. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 60, 117-126. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2010.10.009>

Jaggi, C. K., Aggarwal K. K. and Goel S.K. (2007), Retailer's optimal ordering policy under two stage trade credit financing.

Paul, A., Pervin, M., Roy, S. K., Weber, G-W and Mirzazadeh, A (2021) Effect of price-sensitive demand and default risk on optimal credit period and cycle time for a deteriorating inventory model. *RLARO Operations Research*, 55(1), 2575-2592. <https://doi.org/10.1051/ro/2020108>

Shen, Q. & Liang, L. (2009). Stackelberg inventory model under two levels of trade credit. *International Joint Conference on Computational Sciences and Optimization*, pp 1034-1038. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSO.2009.11>

Shinkai, T. (2000). Second Mover Disadvantages in a Three-Player Stackelberg Game with Private Information. *J. Econ. Theory*, 90, 293-304. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jeth.1999.2608>

Skouri, K., Papachristos, S. & Goyal, S.K.. (2008). An EOQ model with trade credit period depending on the ordering quantity. *Journal of Information and Optimization Sciences*, 29, 947-961. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02522667.2008.10699847>

Wan, Q., Huang, Y., Yu, C. & Lu, M. (2021). Strategic provision of trade credit in a dual-channel supply chain. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2021, Article ID 9918660. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9918060>

Wang, Y., Sun, X. & Meng, F. (2015). On the Conditional and Partial Trade Credit Policy with Capital Constraints: A Stackelberg Model. *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, 40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2015.04.036>

Wu, C., Liu, X. & Li, A. (2021). A loss-averse retailer–supplier supply chain model under trade credit in a supplier-Stackelberg game. *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation*, 182, 353-365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matcom.2020.10.025>

Wu, C & Zhao, Q. (2017). An uncooperative ordering policy with time-varying price and learning curve for time-varying demand under trade credit. *European Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 11(13), 380-402. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1504/EJIE.2017.084881>

Wu, C., Zhao, Q & Xi, M. (2017). A retailer-supplier supply chain model with trade credit default risk in a supplier-Stackelberg game. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 112(1), 568-575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2017.03.004>

Zhou, Y.W & Zhou, D. (2013)/ Determination of the optimal trade credit policy: a supplier-Stackelberg model. *Journal of the Operational*

Research Society, 64(7), 1030-1048.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1057/jors.2012.102>

Zhang, C. You, M. & Han, G. (2021). Integrated supply chain decisions with credit-linked demand: a Stackelberg approach. *Scientia Iranica*, 28(2), 927-949.

<https://doi.org/10.24200/sci.2019.50342.1646>